

ANALYSIS OF RHYMING IN THE POEMS OF USMON NOSIR AND
EDGAR ALLAN POE

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Annotation. *The primary aim of this article is to depict the importance of rhyme, its origin and patterns, types, more importantly, the analysis of rhyme in the poems of Edgar Allan Poe and Usmon Nosir. As a stylistic device and poetic expression, rhyme is one of the integral part of poems, it serves multiple functions range from emotional expression to aesthetic beauty of a poem, thus leaving lasting effect on the readers.*

Key words: *rhyme, rhyme patterns, rhyme scheme, verse line, poetic expression, full rhyme, half rhyme, internal rhyme, assonance, consonance, rhymed pairs.*

Аннотация. *Основная цель этой статьи - показать значение рифмы, ее происхождение и схемы, типы, и, что особенно важно, анализ рифмы в стихах Эдгара Аллана По и Усмана Носира. Как стилистическое средство и поэтическое выражение, рифма является одной из неотъемлемых частей стихотворений, она выполняет множество функций, от эмоционального выражения до эстетической красоты стихотворения, оставляя тем самым неизгладимое впечатление на читателей.*

Ключевые слова: *рифма, схемы рифмовки, стихотворная строка, поэтическое выражение, полная рифма, неточная рифма, внутренняя рифма, ассонанс, консонанс, рифмованные пары.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolaning asosiy maqsadi qofiya, uning ahamiyati, tarixi, kelib chiqishi va turlari hamda Edgar Allan Poe va Usmon Nosir she'rlarida qoyifaning tahlilini ifodalash hisoblanadi. Stilistik vosita va she'riy ifoda sifatida qofiya she'ning ajralmas qismlaridan biri hisoblanib, u she'ning hissiy ifodasidan tortib, estetik go'zallik beruvchi vosita vazifasini bajaradi va bu orqali o'quvchilarda o'zining ta'sirini qoldiradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *qofiya, qofiya shakllari, qofiya sxemasi, misra, she'riy ifoda, ichki qofiya, mukammal qofiya, unli tovushlar uyg'unligi, undosh tovushlar uyg'inligi, qofiyalangan juftliklar.*

Introduction

Rhyme has been known for many years as a poetic device that can be found, mainly in poetry, prose, proverbs, riddles and tongue twisters. As compared with other stylistic devices this expression has long journey than other devices, and this journey

has begun before the spread of written language, in the folk tales that dates back to many years. Rhyme is not only matching words together but also includes providing musical effect, emphasizing certain words and making them stand out. Rhyme serves as a bridge for poets to reach their audience with predictable, pleasurable and memorable, unforgettable lines. In English poetry, Edgar Allan Poe is one of the prominent poet who draw readers' attention with unique writing style and enchanting rhyming pairs and schemes. In Uzbek poetry, Usmon Nosir exhibits a strong emphasis on rhyme of the poem, thus stands out with his use of rhyme and repetition. Both poets lived in different periods and have unique style in writing, but these poets' poems are same in terms of haunting and melancholic atmosphere that is created by the application of rhyme.

Literature review

As mentioned above, literary works are created with the help of stylistic devices and expressive means which are considered important features. These devices can be in a phonetical, lexical and semantic level and expressions that relate to each level can differ in many ways but they help writers to express their feelings, create aesthetic atmosphere which attract readers' attention. Among them, rhyme is one of the important feature of a poem and it is mainly considered only poetic expression but it can be occasionally used in prose by writers. When it comes to the definition of rhyme, according to Fabb "Rhyme is the representation of pairs of words which are identical in terms of phonological similarity from the last accented vowel to the end of a word".¹ Fabb defined rhyme as words which have familiar phonologically identical sounds which actually come at the end of the verse. Quintilian also states that the rhyme is a type of poetic expression which two or more words receive similar endings at the end of the line.² Rhyme has diverse effects on poems and other literary works. "Besides rhyme's potential effect on aesthetic experience, they are claimed to the influence comprehension and recall of words "says Lea.³ Rhyme, not only connect words and their meanings logically and make structure framework for writers but also aid in memorization and grasp of words. Furthermore, Allopenna states that, this poetic expression seems to contribute to the structural organization of lexico-semantic information in the verse, more precisely, according to the rhyme pattern and type poets

¹Fabb, N., & Sykari, V. (2022). Rhyme in the Languages and Cultures of the World. *Rhyme and Rhyming in Verbal Art, Language, and Song*, 14, 11.

²Dimšić, M. The Analysis of Rhyming Patterns in Edgar Allan Poe's Poem The Raven and Its German and Croatian Translations.

³Lea, R. B., Elfenbein, A., & Rapp, D. N. (2021). Rhyme as resonance in poetry comprehension: An expert–novice study. *Memory & Cognition*, 49(7), 1285-1299.

choose the right words which can be rhyme.⁴ Furthermore, Schlegel gives one of rhymes' function and says "in terms of aesthetic side it attracts our attention and give our brain an opportunity to compare and appreciate the words."⁵

Origin and usage of rhyme

Rhyme developed in Western poetry as a poetic device that combines end consonance, alliteration and end assonance and Aristotle first mentions in his book called "Rhetoric". This poetic device is occasionally found in classical poetry of Greek and Latin, but frequently appeared in the songs and religious verses of Latin in 4th century. The history of rhyme in English language trace back to the 7th century, although, there is not accurate information about when and where it started first. What can be noticed about the origin of rhyme is that it has various and long journey not only in English language but also different countries around the world.

Rhyme types and patterns

Rhyme is commonly used in poetry by poets and Shipley notes that the rhythmic conventions are universally the same in spite of nations and countries.⁶ When a rhyme is considered, many of us only think about one type of rhyme, called perfect rhyme, where words are chosen according to identical sounds like "know" and "snow" or "shake" and "wake. In literature, three types of rhymes are distinguished and vary from each other.

1. *Full rhyme* is also called a perfect rhyme one of the widespread types of rhyme which share the same number of syllables and the similar assonance like, *dog* and *log* or *bore* and *more*.

2. *Half-rhyme*, known as imperfect, near and slant rhyme. In this type of rhyme, words are chosen whether they have similar syllables or identical assonance like *cat* and *hit* (similar syllables and assonance only end of the words, sound *t*).

3. *Internal rhyme*, the rhyme that come in the middle of the verse line not at the end of the line like other types. For example,

Once upon a midnight *dreary*, while I pondered, weak and *weary*; (*dreary* and *weary* are internal rhymes).

Rhymes can be created by poets which means words are chosen owing to the intention and will of the person who is creating literary work but most poets use solid structures called rhyme schemes. When words are chosen according to the rhyme patterns, poets should follow where to use the word that comes as rhyme. Rhyme

⁴Obermeier, C., Menninghaus, W., Von Koppenfels, M., Raettig, T., Schmidt-Kassow, M., Otterbein, S., & Kotz, S. A. (2013). Aesthetic and emotional effects of meter and rhyme in poetry. *Frontiers in psychology*, 4, 34805.

⁵Levine, N. (2018). Rhyme. *Victorian Literature and Culture*, 46(3-4), 844-847.

⁶Shipley, Joseph T. (1953). *Dictionary of World Literature*. Philosophical Library. New York.

scheme is the rhyme patterns that occur at the end of verse line and its three types are used widely in literature, poetry.

Alternate rhyme is the rhyme pattern where words are rhymed in every line like (ABAB) in “Spring” by Marguerite Young.

Envy not Spring her <i>innocence</i>	A
The creature coiled within the <i>womb</i>	B
Has not the high <i>indifference</i>	A
Of one who flowers from a <i>tomb</i>	B

The second type of rhyme scheme is called *enclosed rhyme* (ABBA) and the words as rhyming pairs come middle of other rhymed words as comes in the poem in “The New Colossus” by Emma Lazarus.

Not like the brazen giant of Greek <i>fame</i>	A
With conquering limbs astride from land to <i>land</i>	B
Here at our sea-washed, sunset gates shall <i>stand</i>	B
A mighty woman with a torch, whose <i>flame</i>	A

In the first and fourth line *fame-flame* are rhymes and middle of this words other rhymed words come *land-stand* in the second and third verse line.

The next rhyme scheme is common in poetry and common as coupled rhyme, words are rhymed in each pair of verse lines (AABB). The extract from the poem “Alone” by Edgar Allan Poe can be example to this rhyme pattern.

From childhood’s hour I have not <i>been</i>	A
As others were, I have not <i>seen</i>	A
As others saw, I could not <i>bring</i>	B
My passions from a common <i>spring</i> .	B

In the first verse line, *been*’s rhyming pair *seen* follows in the second line, *bring* and *spring* rhymes in the third and fourth rhyme are put in each pair of lines.

Whether poets create their own rhymes, rhymed words or use rhyme schemes, this poetic device can leave lasting and unforgettable effect on audience, thus aiding poets to make their work more effective.

Analysis of rhyme and rhyme scheme in poems of Edgar Allan Poe and Usmon Nosir

Rhyme is one of the first poetic expression that dates back to the centuries when it was not noticed as an integral part of poems. The occurrence of the rhyme is not only appeared in poetry but also prose, riddles, proverbs and tongue twisters, thus providing aesthetic and emotional effect. Both in Uzbek and English literature, mainly in poetry, the function and influence of rhyme is significant and this can be more noticed when we analyze the works of Edgar Allan Poe and Usmon Nosir.

As a versatile writer, Edgar Allan Poe created works in many genres of literature, but the legacy and contribution in poetry is significant than other fields. His poems and other literary works are considered masterpiece and are read across the world, furthermore, he was the representative of Romanticism who is identified as a central figure of this movement as well.⁷ The poet had already noticed the importance of rhyme in poetry and devoted a whole essay to the significance of this poetic device, discussing and highlighting the features of it. The poems of Edgar Allan Poe show how rhyme can be a tool to reach cohesion between lines, serves as an aesthetic device that draw readers' attention by providing long-lasting effect.

The poem "Alone" by E.A. Poe includes different types of rhyme and schemes and provide us with the beauty this device in-depth.

From childhood's hour I have not *been* (a)
As others were, I have *seen* (a)
As others saw, I could not *bring* (b)
My passions from a common *spring* (b)

The rhyme scheme is put in coupled rhyme AABB (stated in the example), rhyming words come in each pairs of the verse, *been-seen* and *bring-spring*. When the type of rhyme is considered, it can be see that rhyming pairs *been* and *seen*, *bring* and *spring* are full (perfect) rhyme, words have same syllables and assonance.

From the same source I have not *taken* (a)
My sorrow I could not *awaken* (a)
My heart to joy at the same *tone* (b)
And all I loved, I loved *alone* (b)

In this verse lines too, the poet use coupled rhyme, words that come as rhyming pairs *taken* and *awaken* in the first and second lines, *tone* and *alone* in the third and fourth lines. In rhymed pairs we can see that stressed vowel sounds are both identical and it means they are defined as perfect rhyme.

To see other types of rhyme, we can example this line from poem "A dream" by Edgar Allan Poe.

In visions of the dark *night* (a)
I have dreamed of joy *departed* (b)
But a waking dream of life and *light* (a)
Hath left me *broken hearted*. (b)

Poet chose an alternate rhyme scheme for this verse, rhyming pairs come in every line, in this example, *night* and *light* in the first and third lines, *departed* and

⁷Parra, Luz Garcia Ma. (2000). Poe: The Concept of Poetry and Poetic Practice with Reference to the Relationship between The Poetic Principie and Annabel Lee. I.B. Cardenal Lopez de Mendoza. Burgos.

hearted in the second and fourth lines. When we analyze these words according to what type of rhyme they belong to, we can see that *night-light* and *departed-hearted* are full rhymes, equal in the number of syllables and assonance.

Enclosed rhyme is skillfully used in the poem of “To Helen”, rhyming pairs come between other rhyming words and easily attract the reader.

Lo! In yon brilliant window *niche* (a)

How statue like I see thee *stand!* (b)

The agate lamp within thy *hand,* (b)

Ah! Psyche from the regions *which* (a)

Are Holy *Land!* (b)

Edgar Allan Poe’s legacy includes various poets and among them “To Helen” is stands out for its odd rhyme pattern. This poem is written in 1831 and main message of this poem is to celebrate to power of women as it can be concluded in the title of the poem. As we analyze this work, the words *niche* and *which* in the first and fourth lines, *stand*, *hand* and *land* in the second, third and last lines are rhyming words (ABBAB), in terms of rhyme type we can notice both full and eye rhyme. *Stand*, *land* and *hand* are full rhyme, both words are matched exactly, but *niche* and *which*, these words are chosen in terms of similar pronunciation [*nitʃ*] and [*witʃ*] not because of syllables or consonance and assonance. Simply put, this unusual rhyming pattern and selecting words in different way for example, due to similar pronunciation make the poem more memorable.

As a poetic expression, rhyme is used significantly in the poems of Edgar Allan Poe and served one key element to make poems more pleasurable and unforgettable for the readers.

Uzbek literature is famous mainly for its poetry and rhyme is the key part of this genre. Rhyme has been used in Uzbek poetry for many years and still most poets organize rhyming pairs according to rhyme types and schemes to evoke an emotional response in the audience. Erkin Vohidov, Anvar Obidjon, Muhammad Yusuf, G’afur G’ulom, To’ra Sulaymon, Usmon Nosir and Hamid Olimjon are one of the best poets of Uzbek poetry whose poems include remarkable examples of rhyme. Among these poets, Usmon Nosir’s literary legacy attract considerable attention in many ways like the structure, organization, logical connection, the meaning that the poet is going to deliver and rhyme. In many Usmon Nosir’s poems regardless of its theme and structure we can see beautiful application and examples of rhyme. Usmon Nosir, as an experienced poet not only skillfully use rhyme but also we can see different types and schemes in one masterpiece. “Again to my verse” is a glaring example to see how this types and rhymes can come naturally together to provoke audiences’ emotions toward the poem and the writer.

My verse! Again yourself you are *kind!* (a)
Blooms feel mean when you are in the *park.* (b)
My dear life, that is what you *find,* (a)
And live in soul as being *spark.* (b)

For the poet, choosing and matching rhyming words is the process that requires considerable attention and may take time to put in lines. But, Usmon Nosir matches the words in a way that this pairs leave emotional effect and make the poem more memorable and aesthetic. The words, *kind-find* and *park-spark* are rhyming pairs and similar in terms of syllable, assonant and consonant sounds. The lines are in alternate rhyme scheme, every lines are ended with rhyming pairs, *kind* and *find* in the first and third, *park* and *spark* in the second and fourth verse lines.

You are a pattern- my heart's *sorrow,* (a)
I can not desist to write, you are *hobby* (b)
Will flame be in the loveless *body?* (b)
My verse is well as illness *follow.* (a)

The poet used enclosed rhyme (ABBA) where rhyming pairs *hobby* and *body* in the second and third lines comes between *sorrow* and *follow* in the first and fourth lines. Matching words are chosen according to their similarity in syllable and consonant, vowel sound which means they are considered as perfect rhymes. This extract shows true nature of rhyme and create connection among not only meanings of words but also the poet and the readers. By using different types of rhyme and schemes, Usmon Nosir convey his feelings and abstract notions freely and make his poems distinctive. Rhyme, both in English and Uzbek literature, particularly in poetry, has been central element and in modern poetry too this poetic device's role is significant.

Conclusion. Rhyme has always been one of the integral feature of a poem and when we look back, we can see how this poetic expression's functions have been changed from years to years. In its long history, rhyme appeared as a mnemonic device that assisted people to memorize things easily and today its significance can be noticed in many varieties of literature works. As Pound says "poetry is focused on verbal expressions" and states three main aspects of them: phanopoeia (visual property), melopoeia (musical property) and logopoeia (the direct meaning and "play" figurative meaning of the word in the context).⁸ If all these features are gathered we can notice direct and indirect effect of rhyme in a poem, for instance, its musicality (melapoeia) and similarity in terms of its assonance and consonance (visual feature: vivid and cohesive). For both poets, Edgar Allan Poe and Usmon Nosir, rhyme was a key to

⁸Pound, E., & Materer, T. (1991). *The Selected Letters of Ezra Pound to John Quinn: 1915–1924* (Vol. 25). Duke University Press.

achieve their desired effect and in their poems these poets demonstrated how rhyme transcends mere sound.

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